

Economics and Business Quarterly Reviews

Kamil, K., Widyatuti, T., Ahmar, N., & Zulkifli. (2023). Determinants Audit Report Delay and Its Effects on Investor Reaction in Public Companies in Indonesia. *Economics and Business Quarterly Reviews*, 6(1), 124-139.

ISSN 2775-9237

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1992.06.01.491

The online version of this article can be found at:
<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

The *Journal of Economics and Business* is an Open Access publication. It may be read, copied, and distributed free of charge according to the conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

The Asian Institute of Research *Journal of Economics and Business* is a peer-reviewed International Journal. The journal covers scholarly articles in the fields of Economics and Business, which includes, but is not limited to, Business Economics (Micro and Macro), Finance, Management, Marketing, Business Law, Entrepreneurship, Behavioral and Health Economics, Government Taxation and Regulations, Financial Markets, International Economics, Investment, and Economic Development. As the journal is Open Access, it ensures high visibility and the increase of citations for all research articles published. The *Journal of Economics and Business* aims to facilitate scholarly work on recent theoretical and practical aspects of Economics and Business.

ASIAN INSTITUTE OF RESEARCH
Connecting Scholars Worldwide

Determinants Audit Report Delay and Its Effects on Investor Reaction in Public Companies in Indonesia

Krishna Kamil¹, Tri Widyastuti², Nurmala Ahmar³, Zulkifli⁴

¹ Department of Accounting, Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Ekonomi Indonesia, Jakarta, Indonesia

² FEB Universitas Bhayangkara Jakarta Raya, Indonesia

^{3,4} FEB Universitas Pancasila, Jakarta, Indonesia

Correspondence: Krishna Kamil. Tel: 08161155592. E-mail: krishna_kamil@stei.ac.id,

Abstract

The audit report delay cause problems of performance appraisal for all audited companies following the investors' response negatively to the audited report. The consequences of these report delay make distrust of stakeholders, so the delay of audited report need to be minimized in order for all companies to be trusted in financial statement reports. The aim of this research is to explore the determinants of audit reporting delay in Indonesian stock exchange, especially on development boards. The exploration is then continued by examining the effects of audit report delay in order to respond to investors' negative impressions. Method of research used in this research is the exposure of facts on testing the application of GCG, financial performance. The factors used in this research were audit report delay and auditor's opinion, investor response proxy by share price. The outcome of the research indicates that GCG and legal compliance pressures have a negative and significant effect on audit reporting delay, while financial performance has a positive and significant impact on audit reporting delay, moderating factors such as legal compliance pressures and KAP size has no effect on audit reporting delay. Audit reporting delay and independent auditor reports affect investor response, while legal compliance pressure and financial performance through audit reporting delay affects investor response.

Keywords: Audit Reporting Delay, Legal Compliance Pressure, Restatement, Company Size, Number of Subsidiaries, Audit Firm Size, Auditor Opinion, Investor Reaction

1. Introduction

One of the obligations of issuers or public companies is to publish financial reports that have been prepared according to financial accounting standards in Indonesia and have also been audited by public accountants registered with the Indonesian Institute of Certified Public Accountants and the Financial Services Authority (OJK). financial audit to OJK. In OJK Regulation (POJK) Number 13/2017 dated 27 March 2017 concerning the Use of Public Accountants (AP) and Audit Firms (KAP), companies listed on the capital market are required to use audit firms registered with OJK and the determination is made through a meeting Annual General Shareholders (AGMS), based on recommendations from the audit committee and the board of commissioners. Auditors and

companies listed on the capital market have a great responsibility to be able to submit their audited financial reports to OJK in a timely manner. This issue has received attention from the supervisory authorities. For example, the US Securities and Exchange Commission has gradually reduced the 10-K filing period for expedited audit submission of Financial Statements from 90 days after the end of the financial reporting year to 60 days over a three-year period. In accordance with the Financial Services Authority Regulation Number: 29/POJK/2016 concerning Submission of the Annual Report of Issuers or Public Companies, it is stated that every public company listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) is required to submit an annual report to the Financial Services Authority, no later than 4 (four) months after the end of the financial year or April 30 of the following year. OJK has revised regulations regarding the submission of annual financial reports.

Phenomena related to violations of provisions and delays in submitting audited financial reports to the IDX and OJK still occur. Initial observations of company data that have not submitted audited financial statements for the 2012 - 2020 financial year, companies that are late in submitting audit financial reports have decreased, which in the previous year (2015) 63 companies became 10 companies (2018), a significant decrease as a result of relaxation from end of March to end of April. As for the 2019 and 2020 audited financial reports, there was an increase in 80 companies and 96 companies respectively, data as of June 11, 2021. The Financial Services Authority provides relaxation regarding the submission of audited financial reports in line with the status of certain COVID-19 emergencies set by the government until May 31, 2020. (SP 18/DHMS/OJK/III/2020 dated March 18, 2020 regarding the press release OJK loosened the deadline for submitting audited financial reports as an effort to adjust to the emergency conditions due to the Corona virus in Indonesia).

Factors that affect the delay in audit reports are Good Corporate Governance, Financial Performance, Size of Public Accounting Firms. Factors that influence investor reactions are the delay in audit reports and independent auditor reports.

The object of research is companies in the mining, oil and gas industry sectors on the IDX development board due to the average delay in audit reports above 100 days and with an average share price of at least Rp.50 per share (observation period from 2014 to 2020).

Most of previous studies examined the cause of the delay in the audit report can come from good corporate governance, the issuer's financial performance is not good such as the amount of debt is greater than the total equity, accumulated losses, the number of subsidiaries and originating from the CPA such as the audit process and the expertise of auditors and public accounting firms, and legal compliance pressure as moderating. Investor reactions are influenced by one of them the delay in audit reports and independent auditor reports which have an impact on delaying the distribution of dividends received by investors, causing a tendency to sell their shares, which will affect decision making, as well as investor confidence in the company because this delay can indicate that the company is in a state of crisis, and in unfavorable financial condition, as well as may result in loss of relevance and usefulness of financial information This studied focus in Indonesia especially on the IDX and in the context of audit report delay, legal compliance pressure and investor reactions.

Therefore, this paper aims to study "Determinants of Audit Report Delay and Its Effect on Investor Reaction in Public Companies in Indonesia."

2. Literature Review

2.1. Effect of good corporate governance on audit report delay

Good Corporate Governance (GCG) is a set of relationships between company management, the board of commissioners, shareholders and other stakeholders (OECD, 2005). GCG is basically concerned with the way all stakeholders strive to ensure that managers and other internal employees always take appropriate steps or adopt mechanisms that protect stakeholder interests.

GCG can affect the delay in the company's audit report. (Cohen & Leventis 2013), (Nor et al. 2010), (Ilabaya &

Christian, 2014), (Afify 2009), (Apadore & Noor 2013), (Hashim & Rahman 2011), (Azubike & Anggreh 2014), (Lailah, F. 2016) shows that, Good corporate governance has an effect on the delay in audit reports. Therefore, it could be hypothesized that:

Hypothesis 1: Good corporate governance affects the delay in audit reports.

2.2 Effect of legal compliance pressure on audit report delay

The pressure of legal compliance means the pressure of submission, obedience, the condition of a person being submissive to the rules of the game (law) that apply in this case the written law. This obedience or obedience is based on the awareness that written laws or statutory regulations have various kinds of juridical powers. With the pressure of legal compliance, the company has hope of a reward and an effort to avoid punishment that may arise if someone violates the provisions of the law.

Lailah, F (2016) shows that GCG has a significant effect on audit report delays (ARL) before and after using legal compliance as a moderating variable. Na'im (1999) proves that companies that do not comply with punctuality regulations are caused by low profitability, financial difficulties, insignificantly influencing behavior on (timeliness) of company financial reporting. Therefore, it could be hypothesized that:

Hypothesis 2: Legal compliance pressures affect the delay in audit reports.

2.3 The effect of good corporate governance moderated by legal compliance pressure on audit report delays

GCG monitors the work carried out by external auditors and puts pressure on legal compliance not to delay the financial reporting of public companies. SEC (regulators) in several countries have established regulations regarding the time limit for the presentation of financial statements in order to reduce delays in the presentation of financial statements by many public companies (Lambert et al. 2013). The Indonesia Stock Exchange has also set rules regarding the deadline for the presentation of financial statements for listed companies, which is April 30 of the following year after the date of the end of the financial statements. The deadline for presenting these financial statements is a pressure for companies to reduce audit report delays, because companies that do not comply with these regulations will be subject to sanctions (POJK No.29/POJK.04/2016). Therefore, it could be hypothesized that:

Hypothesis 3: Good corporate governance moderated by legal compliance pressure affects the delay in audit reports

2.4 Effect of financial performance on audit report delay

Financial performance, Vuko and Cular (2014), the results of the study show that there is a significant positive effect on the delay in audit reports. The results of the research by Sawitri & Budiarta (2018), Suparsada & Putri (2017) conclude that financial performance has a negative influence on the delay in submitting audited financial statements. Cullinan (2003) research results show that financial performance with audit report delays has a significant negative relationship. The auditor is responsible for upholding professional scepticism in all planning and conducting audits, in short the auditor must remain vigilant of the possibility of material misstatement whether due to fraud or errors in all planning and audit implementation. Therefore, it could be hypothesized that:

Hypothesis 4: Financial performance affects the delay in audit reports

2.5 The effect of the size of audit firm (KAP) on audit report delay

The size of an Audit Firm (KAP) can be measured based on the number of employees, number of clients, and reputation. Large Audit Firms have a large number of employees, can audit more efficiently and effectively, have a flexible schedule that allows them to complete audits on time, and have a stronger incentive to complete their audits faster in order to maintain their reputation. The size of the KAP is based on the number of partners in a KAP, which is divided into large, medium and small KAPs. The more the number of partners in one KAP, it can be said that the reputation of the KAP is getting higher because with many partners, there will be more opportunities to discuss among partners in solving audit cases and maintaining audit quality control standards so

that the audit quality is higher and more trusted by the public.

The KAP size measure of the length of delay in audit reports according to Ashton et al. (1989) Hossain and Taylor (1998) Ahmad and Kamarudin (2003); Che-Ahmad and Abidin (2008) found that there is a significant relationship between KAP size and audit report delay. Therefore, it could be hypothesized that:

Hypothesis 5: The size of audit firm will affect the delay in the audit report

2.6 Effect of late audit report on investor reaction.

The delay in audit reports can affect market participants to react more quickly in decision making so that the information has value in the eyes of investors. The longer the delay in the publication of the audited annual financial statements, the potential for economic uncertainty expected by the market will be.

The timely submission of audited financial reports is one of the prerequisites for increasing the company's stock market price on the Indonesia Stock Exchange. Givoly and Palmon (1982), Owusu-Ansah (2000) asserted that late submission of financial statements is the single most important determinant of the timeliness of submitting audited financial statements related to earnings information, which in turn, determines the market reaction to earnings information. The length of time for completion of the audit will affect the market reaction to delays in the submission of financial statements. Therefore, it could be hypothesized that:

Hypothesis 6: The delay in the audit report affects the reaction of investors

2.7 The effect of independent auditors' reports on investor reactions.

The Independent Auditor's Report (LAI) is issued in relation to the going concern paragraph (SA570, 2013) – going concern is generally included in the paragraph emphasizing a matter (emphasis on matters – eom) (SA706,2013). Based on signal theory, the company will provide a signal for users of financial statements in the form of information related to the company's financial performance, one of which is an independent auditor's report provided by a public accountant. The independent auditor's report with a going concern paragraph by the company is considered a negative signal for investors because the company is facing a problem that will have an impact on the survival of the company. The published information will provide a signal for users of financial statements, especially investors in making decisions.

The provision of an unqualified opinion with a going concern paragraph (SA570, 2013) – going concern - will affect the reaction of investors. The reaction of investors to the acceptance of going concern audit opinion. Blay and Geiger (2001) Herbohn, et al. (2007) Menon and Williams (2010) found that investors reacted significantly negatively to the acceptance of going concern audit opinions. Therefore, it could be hypothesized that:

Hypothesis 7: The independent auditor's report has an effect on investors' reactions.

2.8 The effect of Good Corporate Governance on investor reactions through delays in audit reports of public companies in Indonesia.

Good Corporate Governance on Investor reactions through delays in audit reports of public companies is one of the prerequisites for increasing the market price of company shares on the Indonesia Stock Exchange.

Givoly and Palmon (1982) asserted that Good Corporate Governance through audit report lag is one of the most important determinants of the timely submission of audited financial statements related to earnings information, which in turn, determines the market reaction to earnings information. The length of time for completion of the audit will affect the market reaction to delays in the submission of financial statements.

Owusu-Ansah (2000) states that timely financial reporting is important to mitigate insider trading and rumors in the capital markets of developing countries. So that investors can more quickly obtain financial information as a basis for decision making and adapt to capital market developments, especially in Indonesia. Therefore, it could be hypothesized that:

Hypothesis 8: Good Corporate Governance has an effect on investor reactions through delays in audit reports of

public companies in Indonesia.

2.9 Effect of legal compliance pressures on Investor Reaction through delays in audit reports of public companies in Indonesia.

The Financial Services Authority in several countries has set regulations regarding the deadline for submitting audited financial statements in order to reduce delays in the presentation of financial statements by many public companies (Lambert et al. 2013). Therefore, OJK has also set rules regarding the deadline for submitting audited financial reports for registered companies, which is April 30 of the following year after the end of the financial report date. The deadline for presenting these financial statements is a pressure for companies to reduce delays in audit reports of public companies in Indonesia, because companies that do not comply with these regulations will be subject to sanctions (POJK No.29/POJK.04/2016). To see the indirect effect, the legal compliance pressure variable is tested as a moderating variable. Therefore, it could be hypothesized that:

Hypothesis 9: Legal compliance pressures affect investor reactions through delays in audit reports of public companies in Indonesia.

2.10 The effect of good corporate governance is moderated by legal compliance pressures on investor reactions through delays in audit reports.

Good corporate governance moderated by legal compliance pressures has an influence on investor reactions through delays in audit reports. According to Fujianti (2016), good corporate governance moderated by legal compliance pressures has insignificant effect on investor reactions through delays in audit reports. Therefore, it could be hypothesized that:

Hypothesis 10: Good Corporate Governance moderated by legal compliance pressures affecting investor reactions through delays in audit reports of public companies in Indonesia.

2.11 Effect of financial performance on investor reactions through delays in audit reports of public companies in Indonesia.

Financial performance which is proxied by the Debt to Equity Ratio, Restatement, the number of subsidiaries and company size has an effect on investor reactions through delays in audit reports. The existence of information that is relevant to a stock encourages investor reactions that affect stock prices. But not all stock markets are efficient, but it could be in a weak or semi-efficient form.

Cullinan (2003) Kennedy et al. (2012) Vuko and Cular (2014), the results of the study show that financial performance through delays in audit reports has a significant effect on investor reactions. Therefore, it could be hypothesized that:

Hypothesis 11: Financial performance affects investors' reactions through delays in audit reports of public companies in Indonesia.

2.12 The effect of the size of audit firm on investor reactions through the delay in audit reports of public companies in Indonesia.

Pourali, et al. (2013) states that there is a positive effect of KAP size through delays in audit reports on investor reactions. When investors know that a company's financial statements have been audited by a public accounting firm, investors will trust the results of an independent audit report published by the company on the Stock Exchange. So the size of the public accounting firm has an indirect effect on investor reactions through delays in audit reports.

The size of the KAP, according to research, found a public accounting firm to be positive but not significant. (Türel & Tungcay, 2014), that late audit reporting is negatively related to the use of Big 4 auditors and unmodified audit opinion. (Lee, 2008). Based on the following research, it was found that the auditor's professional skills and auditor's educational background had a significant effect on the delay in reporting local government financial report audits. (Sutaryo & Laser, 2015). Apadore and Noor (2013) show that KAP size through delays in audit reports has no effect on investor reactions. Therefore, it could be hypothesized that:

Hypothesis 12: The size of the audit firm has an effect on investor reactions through the delay in audit reports of public companies in Indonesia

3. Method

This research is focused on empirically testing the hypothesis of the model developed based on the proposed theoretical model. Identification and integration of the determinant variables that affect the delay in audit reports such as good corporate governance, financial performance and the size of the public accounting firm. The moderating variable is legal compliance pressure. Furthermore, the effect of delay in audit reports on investor reactions with other endogenous variables is independent auditor reports.

The model on the determinant variables that affect the delay in audit reports such as good corporate governance, financial performance and the size of the public accounting firm. The moderating variable is legal compliance pressure. Furthermore, the effect of delay in audit reports on investor reactions with other endogenous variables is independent auditor reports as follows:

Figure 1: Model on the determinant variables

Fig. 1. Model on the determinant variables that affect the delay in audit reports such as good corporate governance, financial performance and the size of the public accounting firm. The moderating variable is legal compliance pressure. Furthermore, the effect of delay in audit reports on investor reactions with other endogenous variables is independent auditor reports.

A summary of variable operationalization can be seen in the following table :

Table 1: Variables Measurement, sub-variables and Operational Variables

No	Variable	Proxy	Indicator	Measurement	Scale
1.	delays in audit reports (ARL)		Length of Audit Completion	The date in the Independent Auditor's Report minus the financial year closing date. Ln Day Length	Nominal
2.	Good Corporate Governance (GCG)	DK	Board of commissioners size	$\sum$ Board of commissioners	Nominal
		KKA	Audit committee expertise	$\sum$ Audit committee expertise / $\sum$ Audit committee (%)	Ratio
3.	Legal compliance pressures (TKH)		Pressure from the Indonesia Stock Exchange and OJK which have set rules regarding the deadline for presentation of financial statements for registered companies	2 = On time 1 = Late	Ratio
4.	Financial performance (KK)	DER	Debt to equity ratio	$DER = \frac{Total Liabilitas}{Total Ekuitas}$	Ratio
		RES	Restatement	2= restatement 1= no restatement	Nominal
		SUB	Number of subsidiaries (<i>Subsidiary</i>)	$\sum$ Number of subsidiarie.	Nominal
		UP	Total aset	Ln Total Aset	Nominal
5.	the size of the public accounting firm (KAP)		group number of partners in one public accounting firm	1=Partner 1, 2=Partner 2 s.d. 10, 3=Partner 11 s.d. 20, 4=Partner $\geq$ 20	Interval
6.	Independent auditor's report (LAI)		Independent Auditor's Report with going concern paragraphs	2= Opinion modification with going concern 1 = No	Nominal
7.	investor reactions (RI)	PRICE	Stock price	Stock price at the end of the month the financial statements are published.	Nominal

3.1. Research Hypothesis

The statistical hypothesis is expressed as follows:

- H₁: Good corporate governance has a positive and significant influence on the delay in audit reports.
- H₂: the pressure of legal compliance has a positive and significant influence on the delay in the audit report.
- H₃: Good corporate governance moderated by legal compliance pressures has a positive and significant influence on late audit reports.
- H₄: Financial performance has a positive and significant influence on audit report delays.
- H₅: Size of the public accounting firm has a positive and significant influence on the delay in audit reports.
- H₆: Delay in audit reports has a positive and significant influence on investor reactions.
- H₇: Independent auditor's report has a positive and significant influence on investor reactions.

- H₈: Good Corporate Governance has a positive and significant influence to investors' reactions through delays in audit reports.
 - H₉: Legal compliance pressures have a positive and significant influence on investor reactions through delays in audit reports.
 - H₁₀: Good Corporate Governance moderated by legal compliance pressures has a positive and significant influence on investor reactions through delays in audit reports.
 - H₁₁: Financial performance has a positive and significant influence on investor reactions through delays in Audit Reports.
- H₁₂: the size of the public accounting firm has a positive and significant influence on the reaction of investors through the delay in audit reports.

3.2. Methods

The research population is all companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) from 2014 to 2020 as many as 641 issuers listed on the IDX in 2014. In 2020 there are 70 companies that have not submitted audited financial statements, so the population after deducting those that have not submitted audited reports to 571 issuers. The target population of the research are companies in the mining, oil and gas industry (29), which are listed on the IDX in 2014. The total population of the research target is 33 companies, both on the main board and on the developer board. The research sample consists of 16 companies (issuers) listed on the development board, namely issuers are still in the early stages and have net tangible assets of at least ID 5 billion. According to the criteria determined from 29 companies in the mining, oil and gas industry, which are listed on the IDX development board, there are 15 companies in the sample with seven years of observation. So the total sample of this study amounted to 100. Data collection techniques using secondary data obtained from the sample company websites and audited financial reports that have been published on the IDX website and then processed or calculated to obtain research variables determined according to the background of the research problem, research questions, and research objectives to be realized. The data collected from secondary data is tabulated, then it will be processed using *SmartPLS3.0*.

The statistical tool used for evaluating and interpreting the secondary data into meaningful information for resulting analysis is PLS Structural Equation Modelling (SEM PLS- *SmartPLS3.0* program). Data analysis methods used are:

- Outer Model Analysis (Validity Test and Reliability Test)
- Inner Model Analysis (Determination-RSquare Adjusted Coefficient)
- Hypothesis Test (t test).

4. Result and Discussion

4.1. Outer Model Analysis

1) Convergent validity: Validity is the accuracy of an instrument in measuring what you want to measure, whether the instrument used to measure the construct can really measure the construct correctly. In this study, the loading factor limit of 0.6 will be used. The following is the *SmartPLS3.0* output for the outer loadings generated in this study:

Figure 2: Outer loadings value

Based on the figure above, it is known that each of the research variable indicators has a value of outer loading > 0.7. There are also those whose indicator values are 0.5 – 0.6 which are still acceptable, except for the DER (Debt to Equity Ratio) indicator. All of the above data is considered sufficient to meet the convergent validity requirements, all indicators are declared feasible or valid for research use and can be used for further analysis. The audit committee expertise indicator from the financial performance variable outer loading is 0.801 and the subsidiary indicator from good corporate governance outer loading is 0.874, indicating that it is feasible or valid.

2) Discriminant Validity: Discriminant validity is done to ensure that each concept of each latent variable is different from other variables. Can fulfill discriminant validity if each loading value of each indicator of a latent variable has the largest loading value compared to other loading values on other latent variables. Here are the results of the discriminant validity of the SmartPLS program:

Table 2: Cross Loadings Value

	ARL	GCG	TKH	GCG * TKH	KK	KAP	LAI	RI
DK	-0.251	0.674	0.063	-0.042	0.151	-0.369	0.260	-0.019
KKA	-0.310	0.801	0.348	-0.218	-0.261	0.368	-0.050	0.240
TKH	-0.764	0.296	1.000	-0.369	-0.411	0.280	-0.271	0.247
GCG * TKH	0.291	-0.187	-0.369	1.000	0.043	-0.169	0.153	-0.069
DER	0.000	0.219	-0.006	-0.094	0.103	-0.090	0.169	-0.094
RES	0.331	-0.083	-0.268	0.028	0.706	-0.128	0.105	-0.225
SUB	0.458	-0.086	-0.372	0.028	0.873	-0.278	0.510	-0.281
UP	0.066	-0.029	-0.247	0.107	0.560	-0.252	0.204	-0.062
KAP	-0.176	0.051	0.280	-0.169	-0.278	1.000	-0.143	0.426
ARL	1.000	-0.380	-0.764	0.291	0.483	-0.176	0.311	-0.301
LAI	0.311	0.119	-0.271	0.153	0.420	-0.143	1.000	-0.265
RI	-0.301	0.167	0.247	-0.069	-0.310	0.426	-0.265	1.000

Based on table above, it can be seen that each indicator in the research variable has the largest cross loading value on the variables it forms compared to cross loading value on other variables. Based on the data above, the results obtained, it can be stated that the indicators used in this study have good discriminant validity in compiling their respective variables.

3) Reliability test: In this study reliability testing was carried out by two methods, namely Cronbach Alpha and Composite Reliability with each value > 0.70 so that the construct can be reliable.

Table 3: Reliability Test

	Composite Reliability	Cronbach's Alpha
Good Corporate Governance	0.71	0.18
Legal Compliance Pressure	1.00	1.00
GCG * Legal Compliance Pressure	1.00	1.00
Financial performance	0.68	0.48
Firm Size	1.00	1.00
ARL	1.00	1.00
Independent auditor's report	1.00	1.00
Investor Reaction	1.00	1.00

Based on the table above shows the reliability test results can be seen that the overall statement instrument used to measure the variables analysed in this study was declared reliable, this is seen from the Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability values of all variables studied greater than 0.70, Except for Good Corporate Governance.

A. Inner Model Analysis

Following are the results of the coefficient of determination after being processed with the SmartPLS3.0 program which is presented in the table below:

Table 4: Determinant Coefficient

	R Square
ARL	0.652
Investor Reaction	0.123

Based on table above, it can be seen that the R-Square (R^2) value for the ARL variable is 0.652. Obtaining this value explains that the percentage of ARL can be explained as 65.2%. Then for the value of R-Square (R^2), the investor reaction variable is 0.123. This value explains that the investor's reaction can be explained by 12.3%.

Based on the value Q-Square (Q^2) is 0.695. This shows the magnitude of the diversity of research data that can be explained by the research model is 69.5%. While the remaining 30.5% is explained by other factors that are outside the research model. Thus, from these results, this research model can be declared good.

B. Hypothesis Test

Table 5: Path Coefficient

	Path	P Values	Estimated	Result
H1	Good Corporate Governance -> ARL	0.04	-0.17	Accepted
H2	Legal Compliance Pressure -> ARL	0.00	-0.63	Accepted
H3	GCG * Legal Compliance Pressure -> ARL	0.66	0.03	Rejected
H4	Financial Performance -> ARL	0.01	0.23	Accepted
H5	Firm Size -> ARL	0.22	0.08	Rejected
H6	ARL-> Investor Reaction	0.01	-0.24	Accepted
H7	Independent auditor's report -> Investor Reaction	0.00	-0.19	Accepted
H8	GCG -> ARL -> IR	0.19	0.04	Rejected
H9	Legal Compliance Pressure -> ARL -> IR	0.01	0.15	Accepted
H10	GCG*Legal Compliance Pressure -> ARL -> IR	0.70	0.01	Rejected
H11	Financial Performance -> ARL -> IR	0.10	-0.06	Rejected
H12	KAP -> ARL -> IR	0.30	-0.02	Rejected

Based on table above, it can be seen that of all the hypotheses (H1 – H7) can be accepted because each of the effects shown has a P-Values <0.05. Except for GCG*TKH and public accounting firms. So it can be stated that the dependent variable has a significant direct effect, except for GCG*TKH and public accounting firms. Based on table above, it can be seen that of all the hypotheses(H8-H12), all of them were rejected because each of the effects shown had a P-Values 0.05. Except for the pressure of legal compliance through ARL through ARL, so it

can be stated that the independent variable to the dependent through ARL does not have a significant indirect effect, except for the pressure of financial legal compliance through ARL

C. Good Corporate Governance has a negative effect on the audit report delays.

Based on the above table IV, it is found that GCG proxied by the board of commissioners and increased audit committee expertise will result in shortening the delay in audit reports. The results of this study are in line with the results of research by Faishal and Hadiprajitno (2015); (Hasim and Rahman 2011); and Fama and Jensen (1983).

Based on observations, it can be seen that the more members of the board of commissioners can reduce the delay in submitting audit reports, such as PT Energi Mega Persada Tbk, PT Delta Dunia Makmur Tbk and PT Alfa Energi Investama Tbk. Apart from that, the board of commissioners is an independent commissioner and also serves as chairman of the audit committee. In several listed companies, members of the commissioners have varied experiences, including retired bureaucrats, private companies and retired military/police personnel. So the board of commissioners in general has an influence in reducing the length of submission of audit reports.

The audit committee expertise (KKA) indicator has a significant effect because the audit committee is also a member of the independent commissioner, the chairman of the audit committee is also a member of the commissioner, and members of the audit committee are members appointed from outside the company. As chairman of the audit committee and member of the board of commissioners, he has expertise in accounting, finance and auditing. KKA has no significant negative effect on ARL. The results of this study are in line with the results of Beasley and Salterio (2001) research.

The board of commissioners together with the audit committee review the financial information that will be published by the Company for the authorities related to the financial statements, as well as review the Company's compliance with laws and regulations related to the Company's business activities.

D. Legal compliance pressures have a negative effect on audit report delays.

Based on the table IV above, with the increase in the variable of strong legal compliance pressure will reduce audit report delays (ARL). Indeed, with the submission rules and sanctions due to large delays, the level of compliance increases in the submission of audit reports. Issuers who submitted late audited financial reports had 56 (24.10%) observation periods, thus those who submitted audit reports on time had 176 observations or 76.80% of all observations. This is also accommodated by OJK, which has postponed the length of the Audit Report from 90 days to 120 days. However, a fine that is higher in nominal value is given. The results of this study are consistent with the research of Najihah and Ayoib (2012); Amirul and Md Salleh (2014) who show that the existence of regulations or standards can reduce audit report delays.

E. Good Corporate Governance moderated by legal compliance pressure has no effect on audit report delays.

Based on Table IV above, it is known that legal compliance pressure is not able to moderate Good Corporate Governance as proxied by the board of commissioners and the expertise of the audit committee on the Audit Report, because when viewed from the observed company data, about 24.25% of issuers are not compliant in submitting audit reports. Even though the issuer has been sanctioned, and GCG, in this case the board of commissioners and its organs, has not responded to sanctions from the financial authorities.

F. Financial performance has a positive and significant effect on audit report delays.

Based on Table IV above, the estimated value shown is positive indicating that an increase in unhealthy financial performance will lead to an increase in audit report delays (ARL). The large number of subsidiaries causes delays because each subsidiary must prepare financial statements that are audited by a public accounting firm. After completion of the audited financial statements of the subsidiaries, they are then sent to the parent company for consolidation. The consolidation process takes time because some of the subsidiary businesses are not the same as the parent business and in the consolidation process there is an activity to make an elimination journal so that

double recording does not occur, especially in the income statement and other comprehensive income of each subsidiary. Consolidation of a subsidiary to an entity by itself will increase the size of the company (total assets), because there is a combination of assets.

Based on the observation of sample data, it can be seen that the more subsidiaries and the larger the total assets (company size) can increase the delay in submitting audit reports, such as PT Astrindo Nusantara Infrastruktur Tbk d/h Benakat Integra in 2019 the delay was 157 days and increased compared to last year and 2020 has not submitted an audit report. PT Bumi Resources Tbk delays from 83 days increased to 130 days in 2020, and PT Bumi Resources Mineral was originally delayed by 77 days in 2019 to 119 days in 2020. Related to the delay in audit reports of PT Bumi Resources Tbk and PT Bumi Resources Mineral Tbk both of them are still within the length of time for submission within the non-late period, with a reference of 120 days according to POJK. In general, subsidiaries are audited by a public accounting firm differently from the parent public accounting firm, as a result it can cause a lengthy audit process, because it takes more time to audit the consolidated financial statements.

G. The size of the Public Accounting Firm has no effect on the Audit Report delays.

Based on Table IV above, The size of the KAP does not affect the delay in audit reports, meaning that the size of the KAP partners does not affect the length of submission of audit reports, this is because the audit process for each public accounting firm is the same, namely using audit standards issued by IAPI. Besides that, the audit quality of each KAP for issuers is reviewed by the OJK and P2PK of the Ministry of Finance. So that audit quality for public companies can be maintained. KAPs with the right to audit issuers are evaluated by the OJK for their feasibility. This means that the KAP that audits issuers has passed the OJK assessment and the audit quality is good. The appointment of KAP to audit is carried out by the board of commissioners at the GMS. Thus which KAP is used does not affect the delay in the audit report. The delay in the audit report was caused by the issuer and caused the KAP to be late in submitting it. In completing the audit, there are stages where the audit results are discussed with the issuer's management. At this stage there is a delay in reaching an agreement, which has an impact on delays in the audit report. It is advisable for the auditor (KAP) in carrying out an audit engagement to be able to estimate the duration of audit completion. Thus issuers can reduce delays in submitting audit reports. The results of this study are in line with the research of Boritz and Liu (2006); Lai (2019).

H. The delay in audit reports has a negative effect on investor reactions.

Based on Table IV above, From the results of hypothesis testing it is known that the delay in audit reports on investor reactions has a negative and significant effect. The estimated value which is shown to be negative indicates that the delay in the audit report has a relationship to the reverse investor reaction, that is, increasing the delay in the audit report will affect the reaction of investors so that it can be seen from the drop in the issuer's share price.

Based on the observation of sample data, it can be seen that issuer PT Baramulti Suksessarana Tbk share price of IDR 1,700 decreased from the previous year, PT Bumi Resources Tbk share price increased slightly from the previous year significantly to IDR 74. From the observation of the sample data it is known that the increase in delays in audit reports affects investor reactions where the issuer's share price has fallen from the previous year.

I. The independent auditor's report has a negative effect on investor reactions.

Based on Table IV above, From the results of the hypothesis test, it is known that the estimated value is shown to be negative, indicating that the independent auditor's report has a relationship with the reverse investor reaction, namely by having an independent auditor's report with a paragraph emphasizing one thing - business continuity - will affect investor reaction as seen from the issuer's share price falling. The sub-variable used in the investor reaction variable is stock price, while stock trading volume is not used because the results are negative and conflict with stock prices. Usually the stock price goes up and the volume also goes up.

From the observation of the sample data it is known that the increase in delays in the independent auditor's report affects investor reactions where the issuer's share price has fallen from the previous year. PT Atlas Resource

Indonesia Tbk's share price was Rp. 400 down from the previous year as well as PT Perdana Karya Perkasa Tbk's share price of Rp. 70 down from the previous year.

The independent auditor's report in the 2017 – 2020 audited financial report still uses the old form, namely the SA 700 version, for the 2021 financial year audit will use the independent audit report version SA700 (revised) where the report form will include an evaluation of business continuity issues, both issuers who are experiencing financial difficulties or not. Thus investors can read and evaluate the feasibility of investing in shares in the capital market

J. Good Corporate Governance has no effect on investor reactions through audit report delays.

Based on Table IV above, the estimated value shown is positive indicating that that Good Corporate Governance on investor reactions through delays in audit reports has an insignificant unidirectional relationship. So the increase or decrease in Good Corporate Governance through delays in audit reports has no effect on investor reactions, this is because investors in making decisions are based on information not only financial information but also non-financial information and rational decision making. The results of this study are also in line with the findings of Lestari and Nuryatno (2018).

K. Legal compliance pressure has a positive effect on investor reactions through audit report delays.

Based on Table IV above, From the results of the hypothesis testing, it is known that the pressure of legal compliance on investor reactions through delays in audit reports has a unidirectional relationship, that is, increasing pressure on legal compliance through delays in audit reports will significantly increase investor reactions. Legal compliance pressure will cause issuers to comply with the law so that they will submit audit reports on time or no later than the end of April of the following year, there are around 76.19% of issuers who are on time and have a significant effect on investor reactions, with signals of rising issuer stock prices.

The form of legal compliance pressure applied by the OJK is in the form of fines and also informing the public by conveying information about issuers who are late to the mass media (newspapers and IDX info). As well as letters addressed directly to the issuer. So issuers should comply with applicable regulations.

Increasing the number of regulations, raises new questions & responsibilities for executives. The reputational crisis triggered by the scandal has made organizations more sensitive to compliance issues. Therefore, in the digital era, violations of compliance quickly go viral in the public and receive severe penalties, both nationally and internationally. At all levels, the demands of companies to conduct business in accordance with the law are increasing. From authorities, investors and customers to suppliers, non-governmental organizations and the media, all stakeholders expect organizations to ensure compliance along the value chain.

Thus the variable pressure of legal compliance through delays in audit reports has a significant positive effect on investor reactions. This means that the presence of the variable pressure on legal compliance is proven to be able to reduce delays in audit reports and ultimately increase investor reactions. The results of this study are consistent with the research of Najihah and Ayoib (2012); Amirul and Md Salleh (2014) which show that the existence of regulations or standards can reduce audit reports.

L. Good Corporate Governance moderated by legal compliance pressures has no effect on investor reactions through audit report delays).

Based on Table IV above, From the results of hypothesis testing, it is known that Good Corporate Governance which is moderated by legal compliance pressure on investor reactions through late audit reports (ARL) has a unidirectional relationship, namely with increased Good Corporate Governance which is proxied by the board of commissioners and audit committee expertise through late audit reports (ARL) will increase investor reaction, but unable to moderate investor reaction. Investors do not react if the audit report is late, this is because investors in making informed decisions are not only financial information but also non-financial information and investor decision making is based on rationality.

Lestari and Nuryatno's research (2018) shows that Good Corporate Governance through the late audit report

variable has no effect on the investor reaction variable. This phenomenon occurs mainly because investors' decisions in the capital market are not only based on audit reports but also consider various external environmental factors related to the company, so that ARL does not affect share prices on the Indonesia Stock Exchange and does not change significantly.

M. Financial performance has no effect on investor reactions through audit report delays..

Based on Table IV above, From the results of hypothesis testing, it is known that financial performance proxied by debt to equity ratio, restatement, number of subsidiaries and company size to investor reactions through late audit reports (ARL) has no significant relationship with increased financial performance through late audit reports (ARL). has no effect on investor reactions, so the increase in financial performance has no effect through delays in audit reports on investor reactions.

N. The size of the Public Accounting Firm has no effect on investor reactions through the Audit Report delays.

Based on Table IV above, From the results of hypothesis testing, it is known that the size of public accounting firms to investor reactions through late audit reports has a unidirectional relationship, that is, increasing the size of public accounting firms through late audit reports (ARL) will increase investor reactions, and affect investor reactions not significantly. So big or small the size of the public accounting firm has no effect on investor reactions through delays in audit reports..

5. Conclusion

This study shows that Good Corporate Governance has a negative effect on the delay in audit reports, legal compliance pressures regulated and determined by the Financial Services Authority have an impact on shortening audit report delays, good corporate governance moderated legal compliance pressures does not strengthen the effect on audit report delays, Financial performance has a significant positive effect on the delay in the audit report, The size of the public accounting firm has no effect on the delay in the audit report, The delay in audit reports has a negative effect on investor reactions, The independent auditor's report has a negative effect on investor reactions, Good Corporate Governance through audit report delays has no effect on investor reactions, Legal compliance pressure through audit report delays has a significant positive effect on investor reactions, Good Corporate Governance moderated legal compliance pressures through audit report delays does not strengthen the effect on investor reactions, Financial performance through the delay in audit reports has no effect on investor reactions, The size of the public accounting firm through the delay in audit reports has no effect on investor reactions.

The recommendations Corporate to restructuring the number of subsidiaries. evaluate which subsidiaries are experiencing losses and deficits and need to be liquidated or merged into other subsidiaries, It is expected to increase paid-in capital, especially those with negative equity, carry out debt restructuring by reducing the principal debt or you can also convert debt into equity, and pay attention to the completion of financial reports with external auditors so that they can submit audit reports in accordance with a predetermined time, which is a minimum of 90 days.

OJK is expected to make maximum regulations on subsidiary companies that can be established by parent companies. The rule was made to nourish the parent company, expected to make regulations on the amount of debt that is reasonable for companies to obtain a maximum of 2X equity, and expected to review the policy regarding the reporting period considering that there are still many companies, especially the mining, oil and gas industry sectors, which are late in submitting their audit reports, until the report submission deadline is approaching.

Investors expected to look at the company's fundamental factors such as audited financial reports and pay attention to DER and the number of subsidiary companies, more in-depth analysis regarding the company whose shares will be purchased. Don't get involved in buying cheap stocks. Choose stocks that have strong fundamentals, If you have already purchased shares and the company is subject to suspension or delisting, then there are two options, namely selling the delisted shares on the negotiating market or waiting for the delisted company to buy back its shares, and diversify stock investment to reduce the impact of losses.

References

- Afify, H.A.E. 2009. Determinants of audit report lag: Does implementing corporate governance have any impact? Empirical evidence from Egypt. *Journal of Applied Accounting Research*. Vol. 10. No. 1, 56– 86. DOI:10.1108/09675420910963397
- Ahmad R.A.R., and Kamarudin K.A., 2003. Audit Delay and the Timeliness of Corporate Reporting: Malaysian Evidence. *Communication Hawaii International Conference on Business, June, University of Hawaii-West Oahu*. <https://www.angelfire.com/journal2/khairul/pdf/timeliness.pdf>
- Amirul, A.M., Md Salleh, M.F . 2014. Convergence to IFRs and Audit Report Lag in Malaysia. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting* Vol.5, No.23, pp : 9-14. <https://www.iiste.org/Journals/index.php/RJFA/article/view/18472>
- Apadore, K. and Noor, MM. 2013. Determinants of Audit Report Lag and Corporate Governance in Malaysia. *International Journal of Business and Management*. Vol. 8. No. 15, 151-163. DOI:10.5539/IJBM.V8N15P151
- Ashton, R. H., Graul, P. R., & Newtown, J. D. 1989. Audit delay and the timeliness of corporate reporting. *Contemporary Accounting Research*, 5(2), 657–673. doi.org/10.1111/j.1911-3846.1989.tb00732.x
- Azubike, J.U.B., Anggreh, M. 2014. Corporate Governance and Audit Delay In Nigerian Quoted Companies. *European Journal of Accounting Auditing and Finance Research* Vol.2, No.10, 22-33. <https://www.eajournals.org>
- Beasley, M. S., & Salterio, S. E. 2001. The relationship between board characteristics and voluntary improvements in audit committee composition and experience. *Contemporary Accounting Research*, 18(4), 539–570. <https://DOI.org/10.1506/RM1J-A0YM-3VMV-TAMV>
- Blay, A.D., and Geiger, M.A.. 2001. Market Expectation for First Time Going Concern Recipients, *Journal of Accounting, Auditing, & Finance*, 16(3), 209-226. https://www.academia.edu/20446687/Market_expectations_for_first_time_going_concern_recipients
- Boritz, J.E.& Liu, G. 2006. Determinants of the Timeliness of Quarterly Reporting: Evidence from Canadian Firms <https://ssrn.com/abstract=875288>.
- Che-Ahmad, Ayoib and Abidin, Shamharir. 2008. Audit Delay of Listed Companies: A Case of Malaysia. *International Business Research*. Vol. 1. No. 4, 32–42. DOI:10.5539/ibr.v1n4p32
- Cohen, S., & Leventis, S. 2013. Effects of Municipal, Auditing and Political Factors on Audit Delay. *Accounting Forum*, 37(1), 40-53. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.accfor.2012.04.002>
- Cullinan, C.P. 2003 Competing Size Theories and Audit Lag: Evidence from Mutual Fund Audits *Journal of the American Academy of Business* vol 3, Issue 1/2, 183-189. https://digitalcommons.bryant.edu/acc_jou/13/
- Fama, E., and Jensen, M. 1983. Separation of ownership and control. *Journal of Law and Economics* 26 (2): 301–325. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/725104>.
- FCGI. 2001. Corporate Governance; GCG. Jakarta: FCGI.
- Givoly, D., and Palmon D.1984. Timeliness of Annual Earning Announcement, Some Empirical Evidence. *The accounting review* 57(3), 486-506. <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/82529823.pdf>
- Hashim and Rahman. 2011. Audit report lag and the Effectiveness of Audit Committee Among Malaysian Listed Companies. *International Bulletin of Business Administration*, 10, 50-66. <http://www.eurojournals.com/>
- Herbohn, K., Ragnathan V, and Garsden, R. 2007. The horse has bolted: Revisiting the market reaction to going concern modifications of audit reports. *Accounting and Finance*, 47(3), 473-493. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-629X.2007.00216.x>
- Hossain, M. A. and Taylor, P. J., 1998. An Examination of Audit Delay. Evidence from Pakistan. *Working Paper, University of Manchester*.<http://www.mahossain.com/pdf/au>
- Ilaboya, O. J., Christian, I. 2014. Corporate Governance and Audit Report Lag in Nigeria. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*. Vol. 4, No. 13; 172-180. http://www.ijhssnet.com/journals/Vol_4_No_13_November_2014/20.pdf
- Kennedy, P.M, Eraghbe, E and Ikhatua, O.J 2012. Determinants of Audit Delay in Nigerian Companies: Empirical Evidence. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, Vol3(6), 46-54. <http://www.iiste.org/>
- Komite Nasional Kebijakan Corporate Governance (KNKCG) 2006. Pedoman Umum Corporate Governance (General Guidelines for Corporate Governance). <https://knkg.or.id/>
- Lailah, F. 2016. Ketaatan Hukum Mampukah Memoderasi Hubungan Good Corporate Governance terhadap Audit Report Lag (Can Legal Compliance Moderate Good Corporate Governance Relations to Audit Report Lag). *National Symposium on Accounting XIX, Lampung*. [http://lib.ibs.ac.id/materi/Prosiding/SNA%20XIX%20\(19\)%20Lampung%202016/makalah/031.pdf](http://lib.ibs.ac.id/materi/Prosiding/SNA%20XIX%20(19)%20Lampung%202016/makalah/031.pdf)
- Lai, K.W. 2019 Audit report lag, audit fees, and audit quality following an audit firm merger: Evidence from Hong Kong, *Journal of International Accounting, Auditing and Taxation*, Vol. 36, pp.1-21
- Lamber, R, Leuz, C & Verrecchia, R.E. 1987. Accounting Information, Disclosure, and the Cost of Capital. *Journal of Accounting Research*, 45(2), 385-420. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/4622036>

- Lee, Ho-Young 2008. A Determinants of Audit report lag: Evidence from Korea – an examination of auditor related factors, *The Journal of Applied Business Research*, 24(2), 27-44. <https://clutejournals.com/index.php/JABR/article/download/1352/1335/5355>
- Lee, H. Y., V. Mande, and M. Son. 2008. A comparison of reporting lags of multinational and domestic firms. *Journal of International Financial Management & Accounting* 19 (1):28-56. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-646X.2008.01015.x>
- Lestari, S.Y&Nuryatno, M, 2018. Factors affecting the Audit Delay and Its Impact on Abnormal Return in Indonesia Stock Exchange, *International Journal of Economics and Finance; Vol. 10, No. 2: 48 – 58*. <https://ideas.repec.org/a/ibn/ijefaa/v10y2018i2p48-56.html>
- Menon, Krishnagopal and David D. Williams. 2010. Investor Reaction to Going Concern Audit Reports, *The Accounting Review*, 85(6), 2075-2105. DOI: 10.2308/accr.2010.85.6.2075
- Na'im, Ainun. 1999. Nilai informasi ketepatanwaktu penyampaian laporan keuangan: analisis empirik regulasi informasi di Indonesia (The value of information on the timeliness of submission of financial reports: an empirical analysis of information regulation in Indonesia). *Jurnal Ekonomi dan Bisnis Indonesia* 14(2), 85-99. <https://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/jieb/article/view/39445>
- Najihah .M.Y and Ayoib.C.A .2012. Adoption of FRS 138 and Audit Delay in Malaysia. *The International Journal of Economics and Finance, American Academy of Business, Cambridge Vol. 4 Num. 1*. DOI:10.5539/ijef.v4n1p167
- Nor, M.N.M., Shafie, R., Wan-Husin, N. 2010. Corporate Governance and Audit Report Lag in Malaysia. *Asian Academy of Management Journal of Accounting and Finance*. Vol. 6, No. 2, 57-84. https://ejournal.usm.my/aamjaf/article/view/aamjaf_vol6-no2-2010_4
- OECD. 2005. Good Corporate Governance. Jakarta: PT Damar Mulia Pustaka.
- Owusu-Ansah, S. 2000. Timeliness of Corporate Financial Reporting in Emerging Capital Markets: Empirical evidence from the Zimbabwe Stock Exchange. *Accounting and Business Research*. No. 30, 241-254. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00014788.2000.9728939>
- Pourali, M.R., Jozi, M., Rostami, K.H, Reza, G. 2013. Investigation of Effective Factors in Audit Delay: Evidence from Tehran Stock Exchange (TSE). *Research Journal of Applied Sciences, Engineering and Technology*. Vol. 5, No. 2, 405-410. <https://maxwellsci.com/jp/mspabstract.php?doi=rjaset.5.4966>
- Sawitri, NMDC & Budiarta, I, 2018 Pengaruh Audit Tenure dan Financial Distress pada Audit Delay dengan Spesialisasi Auditor Sebagai Variabel Pemoderasi.(The Effect of Audit Tenure and Financial Distress on Audit Delay with Auditor Specialization as a Moderating Variable). *E-Jurnal Akuntansi*, vol. 22, no. 3, pp 1965-1991. <https://ojs.unud.ac.id/index.php/Akuntansi/article/view/36807>
- Audit Standard (SPAP/SA): 2013. Indonesian Institute of Certified Public Accountants, Jakarta, Salemba Empat\
- Sutaryo, S., Lase, Y., 2015. Auditor Characteristics and audit delay: Evidence from Indonesian *Regional Governance. Corporate Ownership & Control*, 13(1), 511-514. <https://virtusinterpress.org/Auditors-Characteristics-and-Audit.html>
- Türel, A., Tuncay, F.E., 2016. An Empirical Analysis of Audit Delay in Turkey. *Annales Universitatis Apulensis Series Oeconomica*. 18 (2), 78-87. <https://ideas.repec.org/a/alu/journal/v2y2016i18p7.html>
- Vuko, T., Cular, M., 2014. Finding determinants of audit delay by pooled OLS regression analysis. *Croatian Operational Research Review*, 5(2014), 81-91. <https://hrcak.srce.hr/120194> <https://hrcak.srce.hr/120194>